

Scribd, 2013, 18 February

Oil, water and crater-like landforms of the Libyan Desert

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Italy

The paper is proposing a survey of a region of the Libyan desert, south of the Waha oil field and south-east of the Sarir oil field, using the satellite images from Google Maps. The images reveal several crater-like landforms, which could be subsidence or, perhaps, impact craters.

Libya has large oil and water reserves. The presence of oil is well-known, whereas that of water could be surprising, due to the fact that the country is for the most part a desert. But under the desert surface, the country has fossil water reserves, used for agriculture and human activities. For this purpose, it was created the Great Man-Made River, a network of pipes from the Nubian Sandstone Aquifer System, a fossil aquifer discovered in 1953, when prospecting to find oil in the southern Libya. This network of pipes is considered the world's largest irrigation project. [1]

During a survey with Google Maps, to observe the Great Man-Made River, south of the Waha oil field [2] and south-east of the Sarir oil field [3], I observed some crater-like landforms. In the Figure 1, it is show a map with the locations of these structures. Images of some of them are also given in Figs.2-4, after a processing to enhance their visibility. These structures could be some subsidence craters, created as the roof of a cavity collapses, causing the surface to depress.

Another origin of these craters could be as the result of impacts of solid extraterrestrial bodies with the earth surface. Wikipedia [4] reports a list of four impact craters in Libya: the BP structure, the Arkenu structures, and Kebira and Oasis craters. The BP Structure is so called because it was identified by a BP (then British Petroleum) geological survey team [5]. The crater is 2 km in diameter and its age is estimated to be less than 120 million years [6]. The Arkenu craters are two circular structures with diameters of 10 km and 6.8 km, in the eastern part of the al-Kufrah Basin [7]. They were considered after their discovery as formed by two simultaneous meteorite impacts, because of the presence of impact breccias and other effects of meteoric impact [7]. However, some researchers had proposed that these geological structures are not impact craters, but eroded ring dike complexes [8,9].

Since many of the impact craters are eroded or buried deep below the sand or under the surface of seas, the discovery of new craters is often obtained during the geological surveys to find oil [6]. Moreover, some researchers consider that the link between impact craters and oil not accidental, arguing the impact crater formations able to create some underground traps for oil. As told in [10] and [11], the materials created by an impact often form a porous rock known as breccia, good for trapping and extracting oil. Besides the possibility of being the reservoir of gas and oil, the impact craters can host mineral resources, as told in [12].

A desert soil allows the visual observation with satellites of exposed craters; the four Libyan craters listed by Wikipedia (Arkenu structures, BP structure, Kebira and Oasis craters) are quite visible in the freely available satellite maps. The structures in Figures 2 and 3 look like

impact craters, in particular they look like the Madna (or Talemzane) impact crater in Algeria as seen in the Google Maps. However, Figure 4 seems not coming from an impact.

As previously told, these structures could be due to a phenomenon of subsidence. However, these crater-like structures could be linked to the presence of some ancient lakes, evaporated when the climate became arid or to phreatic activities. In any case, the crater field we can observe in the satellite maps is huge.

References

- [1] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Great_Manmade_River
- [2] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Waha_field
- [3] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sarir_field
- [4] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Impact_craters_of_Libya
- [5] <http://www.passc.net/EarthImpactDatabase/bpstructure.html>
- [6] Another crater discovered by the British Petroleum company is the Silverpit crater, buried structure under the North Sea. Its meteor impact origin was first proposed and widely reported in 2002, by Stewart SA, Allen PJ (2002). A 20-km-diameter multi-ringed impact structure in the North Sea. *Nature* 418 (6897): 520–3; Stewart, S. A. & Allen, P. J. (2005). 3D seismic reflection mapping of the Silverpit multi-ringed crater, North Sea. *Geological Society of America Bulletin* 117 (3): 354–368. On the Silverpit crater an alternative origin has been proposed too by Underhill J.R. (2004). Earth science: an alternative origin for the 'Silverpit crater'. *Nature* 428 (6980): 280.
- [7] Paillou P., A. Rosenqvist A., J.M. Malezieux, B. Reynard, T. Farr, and E. Heggy (2003) Discovery of a double impact crater in Libya: The astrobleme of Arkenu. *Comptes Rendus Geoscience*. vol. 335, no. 15, pp. 1059–1069.
- [8] Cigolini, C, C Laiolo, and M Rossetti (2012) Endogenous and nonimpact origin of the Arkenu circular structures (al-Kufrah basin-SE Libya) *Meteoritics & Planetary Science*. 47(11):1772-1788.
- [9] Di Martino, M, C Cigolini, and L. Orti (2008) Non-impact origin of the Arkenu craters (Libya) *Large Meteorite Impacts and Planetary Evolution IV*, 17–21 August, Vredefort Dome South Africa. abstract no. 3012, Lunar and Planetary Institute, Houston, Texas.
- [10] Michael Paine, *Prospecting for Oil? Look In an Asteroid Crater*, space.com.
- [11] Vladimir G. Kutcherov, *Abiogenic Deep Origin of Hydrocarbons and Oil and Gas Deposits Formation*, in *Hydrocarbon*, Edited by V. Kutcherov and A. Kolesnikov, ISBN 978-953-51-0927-3. This reference is proposing a list of impact craters too.
- [12] W.U. Reimold, C. Koeberl, R.L. Gibson, and B.O. Dressler, *Economic Mineral Deposits in Impact Structures: A Review*, in *Impact Tectonics*, Koeberl, C., and Henkel, H., Eds. (2005), vol. 6, Springer, Heidelberg, ISBN 3-540-24181-7.

Fig.1 Near the Sarir and Waha oil fields, the satellite images show several crater-like structures. The sites of these structures are marked in the map (ACME Mapper).

Fig.2 Crater-like structure as seen by the Google Maps after a processing to increase their visibility.

Fig.3 Another crater-like structure as seen by the Google Maps, after processing..

Fig.4 An interesting structure in the Libyan desert, from the Google Maps after processing.